

Harnessing Discrete Heterogeneous Spatial Organisation for Engineering Design.

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Abstract—Morphogenesis in biological systems demonstrates how spatial organisation and material heterogeneity can be exploited to achieve high levels of functionality and efficiency. In contrast, conventional engineering design and topology optimisation methods often favour homogeneous material distributions, limiting their ability to exploit heterogeneity for multi-objective performance. Incorporating spatially varying material properties into evolutionary design remains challenging due to the complexity of encoding and managing heterogeneous structures. This paper introduces Spatial Organisation Representations (SORs) as a unified framework for encoding material distribution and heterogeneity within evolutionary topology optimisation. SORs provide compact, locality-preserving encodings that define discrete material layouts upon decoding, enabling efficient exploration of large and heterogeneous design spaces. A range of SORs are systematically evaluated against explicit encodings to assess their ability to (i) reproduce known designs and (ii) discover novel, mechanically viable solutions across two engineering design tasks. The results demonstrate that SORs consistently produce structurally coherent and mechanically efficient designs while requiring significantly shorter genome lengths and fewer evaluations than explicit representations. Moreover, locality-preserving SORs exhibit improved scalability and reduced imperfections associated with disconnected or inefficient material layouts. Overall, this work illustrates that SORs offer a biologically inspired and computationally efficient approach to evolutionary topology optimisation, bridging principles from developmental biology with engineering design practice and enabling scalable optimisation of discrete heterogeneous structures.

Index Terms—Engineering design, evolutionary algorithms, spatial organisation, topology optimisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

MORPHOGENESIS, the process by which natural organisms develop intricate structures, relies on the precise coordination of a number of elements, including chemical gradients that drive cell specialisation. This process ultimately leads to the formation of organs with specific functions [1], organised around a genetically-encoded body plan. While foundational to biological systems, recent advancements have applied the principles of morphogenesis to artificial domains, particularly in evolutionary computation for topology optimisation [2], [3].

In engineering design, bioinspired principles of evolution and organisation have been widely applied to develop homogeneous structures, where material properties remain constant across the design space to meet specific requirements [4]. While homogeneous designs offer advantages such as simplified manufacturing and cost efficiency, they often lack adaptability, as a single uniform material may not be the most suitable for diverse functional demands. In contrast, heterogeneous designs can enhance performance by targeting

strength, reducing weight, and function, all exactly where needed. Applications include bridges, vehicle anchor brackets, long-span power cables, and tripartite structures in transportation [5], [6], [7], [8].

This paper introduces Spatial Organisation Representations (SORs) as a unifying abstraction for spatial encodings in evolutionary design, and demonstrates through systematic empirical analysis that locality-preserving SORs offer superior scalability and search efficiency when evolving discrete heterogeneous structures. SORs provide a compact encoding that, upon decoding, defines material distribution and density, enabling efficient topology optimisation and precise control over structural heterogeneity.

The potential of SORs is demonstrated through three complementary evaluations:

- *Representational capability analysis*, via replication of known benchmark designs to assess whether SORs can capture meaningful structural regularities.
- *Application to a static structural domain*, evaluating the ability to generate heterogeneous engineering designs.
- *Application to a dynamic structural domain*, assessing the capacity to produce structurally coherent and functionally effective solutions.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II presents a literature review, covering topics from traditional topology optimisation to the early adoption of Spatial Organisation Representations (SORs). Section III defines SORs and introduces a range of methods for encoding them. Section IV describes experiments designed to evaluate SORs in both replicating existing design solutions and evolving novel ones. Section V discusses the limitations of the current approach and outlines potential directions for future work. Finally, Section VI summarises the main findings and concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In traditional topology optimisation, the design space is typically discretised into a grid of elements, with the optimisation algorithm operating directly on this grid [9]. A threshold is then applied to determine the presence or absence of material in each cell based on its density. While this representation can produce optimised designs, it often involves a large number of design variables, leading to high computational costs. Physical imperfections such as the checkerboarding effect¹, where solid and void cells alternate in a grid-like pattern, may also emerge. These patterns can compromise structural integrity,

¹Section IV-B illustrates this effect when using an explicit encoding.

complicate manufacturing, and typically require additional post-processing to resolve such issues. This paper focuses on evolutionary methods to explore alternative representations and address some of these limitations.

Various representations have been proposed in the literature for using evolutionary algorithms in engineering design, aiming to evolve designs with a relatively low number of design variables or genome lengths, e.g., [10], [4], [11]. A central challenge in developing such representations is to define an encoding that is sufficiently flexible to explore the design space yet sufficiently constrained to allow an EA to converge. These representations include explicit encoding [12], [13], material-mask overlays [14], [15], [16], voronoi [17], grammar-based approaches [18], [19], [20], neuroevolutionary methods [21], [22], [23], [3], [24], and graph-based representations [25], [26]. However, most of these methods assume a binary spatial organisation, focusing on the presence or absence of material. While traditional evolutionary design representations often rely on binary spatial organisation, recent advancements have explored more sophisticated approaches to achieve greater material diversity and improved performance. These methods extend beyond simple material presence or absence, enabling the design of heterogeneous structures with varying material properties (see Table I for a more detailed comparison of representations in the literature).

One of the earliest works on heterogeneous structure optimisation was presented in [27], where an explicit encoding representation was used. In this approach, each voxel in the design space encodes a material property. Later, Baier et al [28] introduced a method where the shapes were predefined but their dimensions were evolvable, and the material types were encoded discretely in the genome. More recently, Kazemi et al [29] proposed a technique where fixed-size trabecular shapes derive their material properties from a continuous density field.

Two examples of heterogeneous structure optimisation used in the field of soft robotics are the neuroevolutionary Compositional Pattern Producing Network (CPPN) and Gaussian Mixtures (GMX). CPPN, first introduced in [30] and later applied to robot evolution in [16], is a neural network variant where evolution not only adjusts the weights and connections but also determines the activation functions for each node. CPPN's output is a density field that governs the discrete spatial organisation in voxel-like soft robots, with subsequent applications highlighted in [31] and [32]. In the GMX approach, a fixed number of Gaussians are evolved, each representing a different material property. This process generates a property probability density field, which can then be decoded to create heterogeneous voxel-like soft robots. More recently, CPPNs have been used to provide a diverse set of initial density designs for topology optimisation [33], [34].

Beyond these examples in robotics, there remains a lack of a formal definition as well as systematic comparison and evaluation of different representations for achieving structural heterogeneity. Moreover, their application in the field of engineering design is still largely unexplored.

Fig. 1. The SOR decoding process translates genome information into final designs. Various spatial representation methods can process the genome as input and generate a density field with different properties, which can then be interpreted in multiple ways to produce the final engineering design.

III. SPATIAL ORGANISATION REPRESENTATIONS (SOR)

This section introduces a definition for SORs and outlines the different ways in which they can be encoded within the genome.

Definition: A Spatial Organisation Representation (SOR) is a method for describing the arrangement of amorphous regions within a given design space as a density field, in which each region may exhibit distinct properties.

An SOR possesses the following key properties:

- 1) *Scalability* size-agnostic, applicable to varying dimensions of the design space.
- 2) *Computational efficiency* achieved through a compact genome, enabling rapid optimisation.
- 3) *Spatial arrangement*, the ability to partition the design space into discrete or continuous regions, allowing flexible manipulation of material distributions and densities to produce different structural configurations.

The density field (D) may be decoded in different ways to generate engineering designs, which are then optimised for specific tasks or applications to evolve effective engineering solutions. Partitioning the design space further supports the manufacturability of the final product. The genome decoding process, which maps a genetic representation to the final design for SORs, is illustrated in Figure 1.

SORs can be categorised into two types: discrete and continuous, each with distinct strengths depending on design requirements and manufacturing constraints.

In discrete SORs, the density field is partitioned into distinct regions, each assigned a specific label indicating, for example, the presence or absence of material or particular material properties, such as those defined by Young's modulus. Classification models can be adapted to generate these discrete fields, offering a structured approach to material assignment. This process is represented in Equation 1, where $D_{x,y}$ denotes the density at a specific point in space, not limited to two dimensions, f is the classification model, $X_{x,y}$ is the corresponding feature vector, and θ represents the classification model parameters. In this case, these parameters are evolvable and encoded in the genome g .

$$D_{x,y} = f(X_{x,y}; \theta) \quad (1)$$

TABLE I

SUMMARY OF EVOLUTIONARY DESIGN REPRESENTATIONS IN THE LITERATURE. REPRESENTATIONS HIGHLIGHTED IN GREY ARE EXCLUDED AS SOR OPTIONS, SINCE THEIR NATURE AND IMPLEMENTATION COMPLEXITY MAKE THEM UNSUITABLE FOR CAPTURING SPATIAL ORGANISATION.

Representation Type	Description	Strengths	Limitations
Explicit [27], [12], [13], [29]	Each voxel or grid cell is directly encoded in the genome.	Simple and intuitive; direct mapping to design space.	Large genome size, poor scalability, limited flexibility.
Material-Mask Overlays [14], [15], [16]	Overlays or masks define material layouts on a base grid.	Reduces genome length; constrains solutions to feasible spaces.	Limited adaptability; resolution fixed by mask definition.
Grammar-Based [18], [19], [20]	Structures generated through recursive grammar expansions.	Compact encoding; captures hierarchy and modularity.	Complex decoding; sensitive to grammar design.
Neuroevolutionary [30], [16], [31], [32], [33], [34]	Neural networks evolve to generate continuous density fields or spatial patterns.	Captures symmetry, repetition, and scalability.	Complex genotype–phenotype mapping; mutations may cause unpredictable effects.
Gaussian Mixtures [31], [32]	Density fields constructed from evolved Gaussian functions.	Compact representation; smooth distributions; supports heterogeneous materials.	Fixed number of Gaussians; limited flexibility for complex structures.
Graph-Based [26], [25]	Designs encoded as graphs of components and their connectivity.	Captures relational/topological properties; supports modularity.	Mapping to manufacturable geometry remains challenging.
k-Nearest Neighbour [35]	Regions assigned based on proximity of points in the design space.	Adaptive and responsive material distributions.	May create irregular or fragmented regions.
Voronoi [17]	Design space divided into regions based on distance to predefined points.	Produces irregular, non-uniform material distributions.	Can create fragmented regions; construction of diagrams is computationally costly.
Superquadrics [36]	Higher-order polynomial functions used to represent shapes.	Effective for smooth, organic geometries.	Overlaps must be handled carefully, otherwise bias in material distribution may arise.

In continuous SORs, the density field varies smoothly without clear boundaries, allowing for gradual transitions in material properties. It is important to note that it is possible to convert between discrete and continuous representations; however, this often requires interpolation or data smoothing techniques, which can alter the fitness landscape by introducing gradient changes or modifying design space complexity.

Choosing between discrete and continuous SORs depends heavily on the application and manufacturing constraints. Processes such as machining and casting typically struggle to accommodate continuous material changes, whereas additive manufacturing techniques such as 3D printing can more easily achieve smooth material transitions. As a result, continuous SORs are often better suited to additive processes, while discrete SORs may align better with more traditional manufacturing methods. This paper focuses exclusively on discrete SORs, while the exploration of continuous SORs is left for future work.

The discrete methods for SORs that this paper explores are:

- 1) *Explicit* encoding: Each element in the grid is explicitly represented in the genome. The genome (g) can be represented as a sequence of integers or a sequence of real numbers, as shown in Equation 2.

$$g = [m_{11}, m_{12}, \dots, m_{1n}, m_{21}, \dots, m_{mn}] \quad (2)$$

The density $D_{x,y}$ is retrieved with a straightforward lookup, as shown in Equation 3.

$$D_{x,y} = g[(x \times n) + y] \quad (3)$$

Here, $x \in \{0, 1, \dots, m\}$ and $y \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, where m and n denote the number of rows and columns of a grid, respectively.

- 2) *Gaussian Mixtures (GMX)*: This method uses a combination of Gaussian probabilistic distributions to model

regions of varying material properties, providing a way to describe amorphous heterogeneous material properties within a structure.

$$g = \{(\mu_k, \Sigma_k) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, k\} \quad (4)$$

The density $D_{\mathbf{x}}$ at spatial location $\mathbf{x} = \{x, y\}$ is computed from the genome using:

$$D_{\mathbf{x}} = \sum_{i=1 \dots K} (\mathbf{x} - \mu_k)^2 / \Sigma_k^2 \quad (5)$$

- 3) *Compositional Pattern Producing Networks (CPPNs)*: A neural network-based representation that encodes spatial patterns by evolving both network weights and activation functions. The output of the network can be interpreted in discrete or continuous values. The density $D_{x,y}$ is estimated using Equation 6. The genome g encodes a network model θ , which takes the spatial coordinates (x, y) and the distance from the centre r as inputs.

$$D_{x,y} = f(x, y, r, \dots; \theta) \quad (6)$$

- 4) *Superquadrics*: Superquadrics is a mathematical representation based on higher-order polynomial functions, commonly used to describe smooth and organic shapes. The genome in Equation 7 encodes 7 parameters for each super quadratic i : position x_i and y_i , shape exponents m_i and n_i , scaling values a_i and b_i and rotation r_i .

$$g = \{(x_i, y_i, m_i, n_i, a_i, b_i, r_i) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, k\} \quad (7)$$

The implicit function for the i -th superquadric is given by:

$$F_i(x, y) = \left(\left| \frac{X_i}{a_i} \right|^{2/m_i} + \left| \frac{Y_i}{b_i} \right|^{2/n_i} \right) \quad (8)$$

where:

$$X_i = (x - x_i) \cos(r_i) + (y - y_i) \sin(r_i) \quad (9)$$

$$Y_i = -(x - x_i) \sin(r_i) + (y - y_i) \cos(r_i) \quad (10)$$

The density $D_{x,y}$ is given by:

$$D_{x,y} = \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbb{I}(F_i(x,y) \leq 1) \quad (11)$$

- 5) *k-Nearest Neighbours (KNN)*: This approach uses a data-driven method to assign regions based on the proximity of points in the design space, often leading to more adaptive and responsive material distributions. The genome here is the coordinates x_i and y_i for each sample n used in the classification model as shown in Equation 12.

$$g = \{(x_i, y_i) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (12)$$

When $k = 1$, the density at (x, y) is assigned from the closest genome point:

$$D_{x,y} = d_{j^*} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$j^* = \operatorname{argmin}_i \|(x, y) - (x_i, y_i)\| \quad (14)$$

i.e., j^* is the index of the nearest neighbour to (x, y) .

- 6) *Voronoi diagrams*: A geometric approach that divides the design space into regions based on distance to a predefined set of points. This representation is useful for creating irregular, non-uniform distributions of materials. The genome is similarly encoded as in Equation 12. The Voronoi cell corresponding to the point (x_i, y_i) is

$$V_i = \{(x, y) \mid (x_i, y_i) \text{ is the closest generator to } (x, y)\} \quad (15)$$

The density at any point (x, y) is then defined as

$$D_{x,y} = d_i, \quad \text{if } (x, y) \in V_i. \quad (16)$$

Each of these methods has its strengths and weaknesses described in Table I, and their applicability depends on the specific engineering problem at hand. By leveraging these SORs, designers can create highly efficient, adaptable, and optimised structures suited to a wide range of applications.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The main objective of the experiments presented in this paper is to illustrate the potential of SORs in engineering design. This is demonstrated through three distinct approaches described below and summarised in Table II.

In the first approach, Section IV-B, a set of SORs is assessed on their ability to replicate existing known solutions. This experiment evaluates whether a representation can capture meaningful structural regularities, a prerequisite for generating novel yet realistic designs.

SORs are used to evolve novel designs for two different applications: a static structure, such as a bracket, and a dynamic structure, such as a gripper. The second approach in Section IV-C evaluates the ability of SORs to generate

novel bracket truss solutions using multiple discrete cross-sectional areas under varying load cases. The third approach in Section IV-D evaluates the ability of SORs to evolve a structurally coherent soft gripper that is capable of lifting a weight.

This paper focuses on exploring different SORs, using the algorithms presented as tools to facilitate this analysis.

TABLE II
EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Experiment	Algorithm	Objectives (minimisation)	SORs
Replicate cross-sectional profiles	GA	Hamming distance	Explicit, KNN, GMX, CPPN, Voronoi, Superquadrics
Evolve truss bracket	NSGA-II	Volume and deflection	KNN
Evolve soft gripper	GA	Number of edges	Explicit and KNN

A. Statistical evaluation methods

In this paper, the Vargha–Delaney A measure [37] is used to quantify the difference between two distributions. In other words, it estimates the probability that a randomly selected value from one distribution is greater or lower than a randomly selected value from another, with values close to 0.5 indicating little to no difference. To assess statistical significance, the Mann–Whitney U test [38] is employed to determine whether the two independent samples originate from the same distribution ($p < 0.05$). The code and scripts used in this study are publicly available².

B. Replication of cross-sectional profiles

The objective of this experiment is to evaluate a set of SORs based on their ability to replicate a target known design. This capability is important, as a representation that can accurately reproduce known designs is more likely to capture meaningful structural regularities and, consequently, has greater potential to generate novel yet realistic solutions. The SORs are assessed by minimising the Hamming distance between the evolved solutions and the target design. The design space is defined as a 20×20 grid comprising 400 cells, where the integer value of each cell represents a material property.

Each SOR can have a different genome length, which plays a critical role in the optimisation process. If the genome is too short, it may be too coarse, resulting in solutions that lack sufficient detail. Conversely, a longer genome expands the exploration landscape but requires significantly more evaluations to search effectively. Therefore, it is important to identify the shortest genome length that still produces high-quality results.

In the experiments presented in this section, the genome g of size n is evenly divided into R segments, with each segment corresponding to a distinct region S_i , as defined in Equation 17. Each region represents a different material property. The size of each segment is calculated as $s = \frac{n}{R}$.

²Website: The code will be made available upon acceptance of the paper.

Fig. 2. The genome is partitioned evenly according to the number of regions or material types. As illustrated in these figures, a genome of size 32 is divided into two halves of 16 genes for two regions; the same principle applies for any number of regions. This genome discretisation is an arbitrary design choice and can be adjusted.

For example, in a genome with 32 design variables and two regions, the first 16 variables define the first region, while the remaining 16 define the second. In a four-region experiment, each region is represented by 8 design variables. This division strategy is an arbitrary design choice and can be adjusted as needed. Figure 2 illustrates the genome partitioning.

$$S_i = \{g_{(i-1)s+1}, g_{(i-1)s+2}, \dots, g_{is}\} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, R \quad (17)$$

The experiments for this section are divided into two parts, where the first set of experiments evaluates the SORs to recreate known cross-sectional profile designs, in this case, cross-sectional profiles with two regions (absence and presence of material). The second set of experiments measures the ability of SORs to recreate designs with four regions. This second experiment represents a situation where multiple materials might be required. For both experiments, the number of design variables for each method was calibrated for a square cross-sectional profile, and then this number of design variables was used to evolve the replication of two unknown targets, in this case, a train rail and an ‘I’ cross-sectional profile. Each of these cross-sectional profiles presents distinct design challenges, ranging from sharp angles to more complex shapes, such as combinations of ovals and rectangles.

The Genetic Algorithm was employed in this section using the default parameters from the pymoo library³, with a budget of 10,000 evaluations distributed across 100 generations and a population size of 100. Due to space constraints, consistency analysis and convergence results are not included in this paper, but available in the supplementary material.⁴

1) *Genome length calibration*: The main objective of these experiments is to determine the genome length for each SOR representation that minimises the Hamming distance error for the square cross-section profile. This is intended to establish a fair basis for comparison between representations.

For each representation, six different genome lengths were evaluated using the robustness analysis technique. Genome lengths that minimise the Hamming distance are highlighted by the grey bars in the results shown in Figure 3 and are described below. The genome length that minimised the Hamming distance between the two experiments (2 regions and 4 regions) was selected for use in the subsequent experiments.

The representations most sensitive to calibration are GMX and KNN, as they exhibit a large A-test difference across most design variable counts when compared to the baseline

configuration, the one that minimises Hamming distance error and is highlighted in grey in Figure 3. This suggests that selecting an appropriate genome length is especially crucial for reducing the Hamming distance for these two representations.

CPPN and Voronoi display similar trends to each other: in the 2-region setup, accuracy improves with an increasing genome length. However, in the 4-region setup, the number of design variables has little influence on accuracy. It is worth noting that a higher number of design variables could have been used for CPPN and Voronoi, but this would negatively impact convergence speed. At this stage, the number of design variables already exceeds that of the explicit representation (400).

The final genome length was selected based on the minimisation of the Hamming distance for both the 2-region and 4-region cases, with no significant difference in A-test values between them. The corresponding values are shown in Table III.

TABLE III
SELECTED GENOME LENGTHS

Explicit	GMX	KNN	Superquadrics	Voronoi	CPPN
400	32	64	42	128	1489

2) *Replication analysis*: This section analyses the performance of each representation in replicating three distinct cross-sectional profiles (square, I, and rail), each presenting unique challenges.

Across the three cross-sectional profiles with two regions, the KNN approach yields the most statistically accurate solutions, using the third smallest genome length (64), as shown in Figure 4a, c and e. The u-test ($p < 0.05$) confirms that the KNN distribution is statistically different from the others.

Similar results are observed for the four-region case, but this time GMX yields the best performance while using fewer design variables (32-length) for the I and rail cross-sectional profiles, as illustrated in Figure 4d and f. The u-test ($p < 0.05$) indicates a statistically significant difference between the GMX and KNN distributions for all the profiles.

One possible reason KNN and GMX yield better results may be that they exhibit a high degree of locality, where minor mutations in the genome lead to minor changes in the phenotype, unlike the other representations, where this is not the case.

It is important to clarify that, in this study, the CPPN uses a fixed network topology, and the reported genome length corresponds to the full set of connection weights, activation functions, and biases of this network. Although CPPNs are commonly evolved using the NeuroEvolution of Augmenting Topologies (NEAT) method [30], which enables topology evolution, allowing structural evolution would introduce an additional source of variability and confound the comparison between representations.

The results shown in this section indicate that overall, KNN provides the best results in four out of the six experimental setups. KNN also has the third shortest genome compared with the rest of the representations. This indicates that care-

³Website: <https://pymoo.org/>

⁴Link: The supplementary material will be made available upon acceptance.

Fig. 3. Six different values of design variables were tested for each representation using the robustness analysis technique, based on the square cross-sectional profile shown in the top-right of the figures. The configuration that resulted in the lowest Hamming distance between the two experiments (2 and 4 regions) was chosen for the subsequent experiments. The grey bars highlight the genome length that minimises the Hamming distance and is used as a baseline for calibration. Note that the different colours represent different materials.

Fig. 4. SOR performance is evaluated based on its ability to replicate six distinct cross-sectional profiles with three different shapes and two different numbers of regions, as shown in the top-right of each figure. The number shown next to each representation indicates the number of design variables in the genome length. The KNN and GMX representations yield the most accurate results while requiring the fewest design variables.

ful attention is needed when choosing the most appropriate representation for the given task.

3) *Qualitative analysis:* Figure 5 shows examples of the most accurate cross-sectional profiles evolved for each representation. Panels (a) and (g) depict the target designs for two and four regions, respectively. Among the representations, KNN produces the most accurate and viable solutions. In contrast, CPPN and Voronoi result in non-cohesive solutions with floating regions, making them unviable. The explicit representation exhibits fewer floating regions, but it suffers from a checkerboarding problem, with alternating cells of different properties. In addition, it is important to highlight some solutions, such as Figure 5j would need fine-tuning in post-processing to reach the final desired target.

4) *Conclusion:* The results in this section demonstrate that the discrete SOR can accurately replicate target solutions using a relatively short genome length, with KNN outperforming others. Selecting an appropriate genome length is essential to maximise performance. Based on these results, the KNN representation is adopted for the remaining experiments in this paper.

C. Evolution of bracket trusses

The experiments in this section aim to evaluate discrete SORs for evolving truss brackets with multiple cross-sectional areas, serving as a proxy for multi-material structures under varying load conditions. In addition, the experiments in this section contrast with those in the previous section, as they do not inherently restrict the algorithm’s ability to generate novelty; unlike the target replication approach, which penalises any deviations.

Composite brackets or multi-material structures have been investigated comprehensively, showing that composite materials can significantly reduce weight, an important consideration in the aerospace and rail transportation industries [5], [7].

Fig. 5. Target known designs and examples of best evolved cross-sectional profiles, for rail example, with different representations.

While evolutionary algorithms have previously been applied to the design of single-material brackets [39], this work extends the approach to more complex, heterogeneous structures. Heterogeneous structures can be evolved to exhibit different behaviour under different load conditions, similar to [40].

This case study focuses on evolving the structure of a bracket with two supports positioned at the bottom-left and top-left corners, as shown in Figure 6a. The brackets are simulated using Calculix [41]. Figure 6b presents the three load cases considered in this paper, along with the corresponding strain energy distribution across the structural members. Darker colours indicate edges that contribute less to alleviating strain energy and therefore have a negative impact on the material usage. A desirable structure would exhibit a more uniform colour distribution, reflecting balanced load distribution across the members.

The optimisation objectives are to minimise material usage and reduce the deflection experienced by the structure. NSGA-II was employed using the default parameters from the pymoo library, with a budget of 100,000 evaluations distributed across 100 generations and a population size of 1000. This evaluation budget was determined based on convergence experiments, which showed that all problems converge before reaching this limit.

A predefined triangular grid, consisting of 10 triangles in width and height, is used to discretise the design space as shown in Figure 6. The cross-sectional area of each structural member within the grid is directly sampled from a discrete density field. The approach follows a similar methodology to that proposed in [29].

This density field is generated using the KNN method, which exhibited the best performance in the previous section. Equation 12 is modified into Equation 18, allowing the incorporation of design variables for each region s_j , thereby enabling the evolution of the cross-sectional area in each region with the exception of the absence of material region.

$$g = \{(x_i, y_i) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, k\} \quad \text{and} \quad \{s_j \mid j = 1, 2, \dots, R\} \quad (18)$$

A total of nine different problems are analysed by combining three load types (vertical, horizontal, and combined)

Fig. 6. The bracket design space is sampled such that each edge in the structure is derived from the density field generated by the SOR.

with material configurations consisting of 2, 3, and 4 regions. The aim is to evaluate the versatility of KNN in providing solutions under varying conditions. Example solutions at the Pareto front for each problem are shown in Figure 7 and 8 and described below.

The first common feature across all structures is that material tends to form along the shortest path between the support points and the loads. This is particularly evident in the 2-region low volume examples; for instance, the material in the top-right corner is removed because it does not help reduce strain energy and instead adds unnecessary volume to the structure as shown in Figure 6.

The second common feature is the use of thicker cross-sectional areas at the support and load points in the 3- and 4-region configurations (Figure 7). This occurs because these areas experience high concentrations of strain energy (Figures 6 and 8). In contrast, edges farther from these points

Fig. 7. Example evolved bracket designs at the final Pareto front for different load conditions and number of regions. Note that the absence of material is treated as a region, and that each colour represents a different thickness, with yellow indicating the greatest thickness and dark green the thinnest. The KNN representation is capable of producing different shapes with different spatial organisation of regions with different cross-sectional areas.

have more evenly distributed strain energy, and thus do not require as much material. These evolved results are similar to what a structural engineer might produce

Lastly, these initial results suggest that differentiating multiple structural regions becomes increasingly beneficial in the segment of the Pareto front associated with minimal deflection. This regional variation contributes to reducing volume while maintaining low deflection. A similar behaviour to that observed in the previous section is seen in the experiments presented here, where visual inspection reveals some truss members that do not appear to contribute to the structure. As a result, post-processing steps may be required to refine these designs.

In summary, the experiments conducted in this section demonstrate the effectiveness of discrete SORs in evolving cross-section areas truss bracket structures subjected to varying load cases. The use of a predefined triangular grid and KNN-generated density field enabled the efficient optimisation of material usage while minimising structural deflection.

Fig. 8. Example evolved bracket designs at the final Pareto front for different load conditions and number of regions. The colour indicates the strain energy in each edge, with darker shades representing lower contribution and lighter shades indicating higher concentrations of strain energy. A desirable structure would exhibit a more uniform colour distribution, reflecting balanced load distribution across the members.

D. Evolution of soft grippers

This experiment compares the performance of explicit and KNN encodings for evolving a soft gripper, with the aim of assessing whether spatial organisation representations can discover structurally coherent, higher-quality solutions using fewer evaluations. Evolution is applied to a single finger, represented as a truss structure consisting of 53 edges, of which the presence or absence of 40 edges is evolvable. The remaining 13 edges form a fixed base, and the second finger is generated as a mirrored copy of the evolved finger. The complete gripper structure and the target object are shown in Figure 9a. The gripper is simulated using Taccel [42]. Material heterogeneity in this experiment is restricted to a binary presence/absence decision. By constraining heterogeneity to this binary case, the experiment isolates the contribution of spatial organisation to search efficiency and structural coherence, without confounding effects arising from continuous or multi-material optimisation. However, the underlying framework does not prevent the use of multiple materials, as demonstrated in the previous section.

The objective of the experiment is to minimise the number

of edges, used as a proxy for material usage within a budget of 200 evaluations. A single Boolean constraint is applied to ensure that the object is successfully lifted and that the finger forms a single connected structure. The explicit and KNN representations are studied in this section, with three different KNN genome lengths of 4, 8, and 12 (Figures 9c, d, and e, respectively).

Fig. 9. Gripper consisting of a pair of fingers, with the object to be grasped (weight) shown at the centre. The best solutions evolved by each algorithm are shown, with the KNN representation producing more structurally coherent solutions using the fewest edges. Videos of these grippers can be found in the supplementary material.

The KNN representation achieves the best performance by minimising the number of edges while requiring the fewest evaluations, as shown in Figures 10. For example, the KNN with a size of 8 found a solution with 26 edges in 4 generations, whereas the explicit representation required 5 generations to reach a solution with 31 edges.

Fig. 10. The lines represent the population mean fitness, while the shaded regions indicate the minimum and maximum fitness values at each generation.

In addition, the KNN representation appears to use edges more efficiently, creating structurally coherent solutions. For example, solutions evolved using the explicit encoding (Figure 9b) contain unconnected or loosely connected edges that may not contribute to structural performance, representing another manifestation of the checkerboarding effect. In contrast, a KNN-evolved solution exhibits a distinctive topology that exploits a subtle geometric feature of the object being lifted. As a result, the gripper experiences reduced bending during grasping (Figure 9e).

In summary, the experiments in this section demonstrate that spatial organisation representations are capable of discovering higher-quality and more structurally coherent solutions with fewer evaluations than the explicit encoding. Notably, one of the evolved structures (Figure 9e) adapts to the geometry of the object being lifted, highlighting the expressive power of the KNN representation.

V. DISCUSSION

This paper demonstrates that Spatial Organisation Representations (SORs) enable compact yet expressive encodings of spatial structure, allowing complex density fields to be generated from relatively short genome lengths. Crucially, this compression does not merely reduce dimensionality, but preserves spatial locality in a way that supports effective evolutionary search. The experimental results show that SORs can both reproduce known engineering designs and discover novel material organisations that minimise volume through strategic spatial allocation.

While SORs provide an efficient route to near-optimal spatial layouts, their primary strength lies in exploration rather than final refinement. For applications requiring highly tuned solutions, computationally intensive methods such as Solid Isotropic Material with Penalisation (SIMP) can be applied as a post-processing step, complementing SOR-based search by fine-tuning material distributions.

The results further suggest that KNN-based SOR is a strong default choice for the class of structural optimisation problems considered here. Its locality-preserving nature aligns well with discrete heterogeneous structures, leading to improved scalability and search efficiency. However, this advantage is contingent on the underlying problem structure, and no single SOR can be expected to be universally superior, as performance depends on material representation, spatial coupling, and design constraints.

Lastly, although discrete SORs can introduce certain manufacturing challenges, they are often easier to fabricate than continuous representations using current additive manufacturing techniques, which typically handle discrete geometries more reliably. Continuous SORs therefore remain an interesting direction for future work, particularly as fabrication technologies mature.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, Spatial Organisation Representations (SORs) are introduced as a unifying framework for spatial encoding in engineering design. Through systematic empirical analysis, it is shown that locality-preserving SORs enable scalable and efficient search when evolving discrete heterogeneous structures. By decoding compact genomes into detailed material distributions and density fields, SORs bridge the gap between low-dimensional representations and high-resolution structural designs.

The results demonstrate that SORs are particularly well suited to early-stage design exploration, where efficient traversal of large, heterogeneous design spaces is essential. Rather

than replacing established optimisation methods, SORs provide a complementary representational layer that prioritises expressivity, scalability, and structural coherence.

Looking ahead, the integration of data-driven techniques such as autoencoders offers a promising route toward more adaptive and generalisable SORs, enabling representations that can transfer across tasks and support increasingly autonomous design processes.

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